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THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF RESTAURANTS IN VISITING MUSEUMS

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Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda madaniy turizm sohasida tub islohotlar òtkazilayotganligi hech kimga sir emas. Shu o'rinda muzeylarning turizm rivojidadagi o'rni beqiyos ekanligini ta'kidlab o'tish joiz. Ushbu maqolada muzeylarga tashrif buyuruvchilar sonini ko'paytirishda ularda tashkil etilayotgan restoranlarning o'rni va ahamiyatiga alohida to'xtalib o'tilgan.

Аннотация: Не секрет, что сегодня в сфере культурного туризма проводятся кардинальные реформы. Здесь следует отметить, что роль музеев в развитии туризма несравнима. В данной статье речь пойдет о роли и значении ресторанов при музеях в увеличении количества посетителей.

Annotation: It is no secret that fundamental reforms are being carried out in the field of cultural tourism today. At this point, it should be noted that the role of museums in the development of tourism is incomparable. This article focuses on the role and importance of restaurants in museums in increasing the number of visitors.

Kalit so'zlar: restoran, muzey, sayyoh, kataloglar, ekskursiya, monografiyalar, mazali san'at, galereya, turizm, kafe, tarix, tashrif.

Ключевые слова: ресторан, музей, турист, каталоги, экскурсия, монографии, изысканное искусство, галерея, туризм, кафе, история, посещение.

Key words: restaurant, museum, tourist, catalogs, excursion, monographs, delicious art, gallery, tourism, cafes, history, visit.

For a long time, we firmly believed that a museum is a temple of art and nothing else. However, today the priorities in the work of many cultural institutions (and not only museums, but also libraries) are changing from preserving exhibits and expanding collections and funds to attracting the attention of the audience, increasing the audience, and fighting for it. First, let's give a brief information about what the museum is. A museum is a scientific, educational institution that collects, preserves, studies and

promotes historical, material and spiritual monuments¹. The treasury of the museum mainly collects material and visual objects, as well as works of art, as well as written sources (manuscripts, printed documents, books of historical value from antiquity to the present). Their activity is shortened, the museum carries out large-scale scientific research and educational work, completes and studies collections, prepares scientific documents, creates the order of preservation and repair of museum objects, publishes monographs, catalogs, guides, based on the scientific method and methodology developed by modern museology. conducts scientific campaigns at expositions. The most important form of working with the audience is the excursion.

Museums - the history of the museum meeting political, scientific, cultural, economic needs goes back to ancient times. The predecessors of the museum were created in the period when the original objects taken from nature and social life began to be kept not for economic purposes and as material wealth, but as memorial certificates and original objects of aesthetic value. Including the Treasury of the Knossos Palace in Crete (16th century BC), the Palace of the Van and the Archives of the Inca Priests (13th-12th centuries BC, China), the Nineveh Palace Library and others. A temple from Kdsim, and later private collections (from the 3rd century BC) mainly contain works of art (galleries of Varres, Sulla, Servilius, Crassus, Lucullus, Pompeii, Caesar and other collections). Various collections were kept in the cathedrals and monasteries of Byzantium, and later in the cathedrals of France, Italy, Germany and other countries. The emergence of a museum charged with scientific tasks in Europe coincides with the Renaissance, the era of great geographical discoveries. During this period, palace collections (kunstkameras, munskabine, etc.) which collected specimens of animal and plant life, minerals, geodetic and astronomical instruments, objects of ethnographic significance, natural, scientific, ethnographic and historical-artistic rare objects, became famous. Initially, the first descriptions of museums and them, as well as theoretical works on museology, appeared during this period. Collections of ancient monuments in Florence (L. Medici, 15th century), Rome (Vatican Museum, 16th century), Dresden (Augustus of Saxony, 16th century) and other places belong to this period. In the 17th-18th centuries, private collections

¹ <https://www.timeout.ru/spb/feature/iskusstvo-so-vkusom-nado-li-otkryvat-restorany-v-muzeyah>.

(historical, archaeological, natural history, art history) were formed, many of which later formed the basis of the state national museum.

In addition, there are several types of museums. Many modern museums are characterized by a combination of research and educational tasks. Unique scientific mass and educational forms of the museum - exposure, exhibitions. In the modern scientific classification, museums are distinguished by types and fields. According to its social function, it is divided into scientific research-enlightenment (which forms the main part of the museum, sometimes they are also called public museum, public museum), research (which performs the function of a specific laboratory under scientific research institutes), and educational museum. It is divided into history, agriculture, natural history, art history, literature, technical and other museums. There are also types of museums such as memorial museums, complex local history. It is worth mentioning that museums were initially widespread in European countries. Objective needs for the development of the museum system with educational and scientific tasks are increasing. The USA, Italy, France, Great Britain, Germany, Russia and other countries have the most advanced museum systems. As the museum enters the international arena, their sphere of influence is expanding. Exchange of exhibitions is in the first place. The museum sends its treasures to different countries of the world, at the same time it receives exhibitions from foreign countries and displays them in the exhibition and museum. The museum helps to expand international cultural relations, makes a great contribution to the mutual enrichment of national cultures and the development of consensus among peoples. Museums have long had tearooms, cafeterias and cafes as part of the services and amenities that make museum visits more interesting, more comfortable and help visitors stay longer. Over the past two decades, these services have flourished and come into their own².

Some museums now have restaurants with attractions like those on the museum walls. As many museum restaurants as there are, surprisingly little has been written about the subject. As museum dining options and experiences proliferate, little research has been done on how the experiences visitors have while dining at the museum affects their overall experience or impressions of the museum. Food helps create memories for many, and the restaurant and gift shop are often the only places where visitors have

² <https://swu.ru/articles/obed-s-muzami-restorany-pri-muzeyah>.

meaningful interaction with the staff. This article aims to examine how museum catering establishments can best serve the museum and the overall experience of museum visitors. Restaurants can make money, they can be an amenity, but do they really enrich your museum experience or help you better understand the museum and its mission?

Initially, after the establishment of the museums, after some time, the first kitchens (restaurants) began to appear in the museums. This process began in the 20th century. This process was opened in order to increase the weight of visitors to the museums and to relieve the tiredness of the visitors and to talk to each other. At that time, there were separate kitchens for men and women. Over the years, the restaurants have become a common complex. At the same time, they wanted to leave confectionery products alone. Recently, the visitors of the Culture 2.0 open exhibition hall discussed a very sensitive topic related to the interaction of museums with the restaurant business and the interpenetration of museum and restaurant atmospheres. Anyone can join the discussion, the event is open to everyone and canceled online. On the eve of the TimeOut meeting, St. Petersburg discussed the prospects for the development of museum restaurants with one of the speakers, during which they asked a few questions to Kathleen LeBesco, Vice President of Strategic Initiatives at Marymount Manhattan College (USA).

At this meeting, the importance of restaurants in museums, whether museums need restaurants or not, and similar issues were considered. For a long time we firmly believed that a museum is a temple of art and nothing else. However, today the priorities in the activities of many cultural institutions (and not only museums, but also libraries) have shifted from preserving exhibits and expanding collections and funds to attracting the attention of the audience - now we have to fight for it! Now it is customary to attract the public, and additional museum services, such as cafes and restaurants, play an important role in positioning the museum as a convenient place for family vacations, friendly meetings and even business negotiations. In the open exhibition hall of Culture 2.0, the speakers discussed whether restaurants and cafes should be included in the museum exposition, whether museum restaurants and cafes have their own characteristics, whether these institutions are suitable for children as an independent recreation center, and similar interesting issues.

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Undoubtedly, such questions will definitely motivate a person to act. At this meeting, the reporter approached Ms. Kathleen.

- Dear Kathleen, For a long time there was a perception that the museum was a temple of art: it was almost a crime to make noise, laugh or eat here. But now, on the contrary, it is customary to attract the viewer. A unique restaurant or unique cafe in a museum is a great way to win over new visitors. How are things going in this regard in your country? In the US, museum restaurants are great bait. It should be assumed that they attract the same category of people - those who have cultural capital and are ready to spend money, perhaps those who come to see this or that exhibition. The best of these restaurants integrate art directly into the dining and recreation areas. Today, American museums rarely hold the view that restaurants are vulgar and that their proximity to art is unacceptable.

- Please give examples of the most original, in your opinion, restaurant concepts in world museums.

- My favorites are the Los Angeles County Museum of Art LACMA Restaurant, muzeyahu takes up 45 pages on the water menu alone, and the cafe at the Hara Museum of Modern Art in Tokyo serves realistic and artistic "patterned cakes". At the same time, most of the restaurants in the museums I've visited resemble each other more than anything else.

- In St. Petersburg, only a few museums delight the public with conceptual delights in their cafes: Museum of Early Modern Art, Faberge Museum... Do you think that a restaurant or cafe should be conceptually connected to a museum? is it located or just a good kitchen and a decent interior?

- Of course, why not?! For me, a restaurant is a space that helps a museum fulfill its interpretive mission.

- Do you think Russian museums can effectively use this tool to attract visitors?

- If the restaurant itself attracts public attention, it can certainly attract a new audience. But this does not guarantee that its visitors will leave the restaurant and go to

explore the rest of the museum. This is the reason for the desire to bring art to the restaurant and create a menu in accordance with the specific exhibitions, so that visitors to the establishment can get to know them, even if they do not leave their table.

– What would you like to talk about in an online discussion on the topic of "Delicious Art"?

– I will talk about the history and functions of restaurants in museums and give examples of how such restaurants help museums fulfill their mission.

– There are many representatives of the restaurant industry among our audience. They can learn something useful for themselves and their business by connecting to an online lecture. Let's find out what exactly they might be interested in?

- Maybe! Perhaps they are interested in listening and reflecting on how the perception of their cuisine changes in the context of museums, which have long been considered "bastions" of taste.

At that moment, this crying came to an end. As you can see, from this open exhibition, it became clear that not only exhibits, but also restaurants have a special place for people to visit museums. After that, the issues of establishment and development of restaurants in world museums became widespread. In this regard, we bring you a new advertisement for the Victoria and Albert Museum in 1988 by the advertising agency Saatchi & Saatchi. The slogan read: "A first class cafe with a good museum". The poster even sparked a debate in the House of Lords over whether the museum could position itself as such. The agency, of course, relied on the fact that the Victoria and Albert Museum was the first to open a cafe in London (in the 1850s). But today's question itself seems to be more evidence of the intelligence of the watchmakers (who, by the way, have their own modern art gallery). After many museums became seriously concerned about the quality of the food served in them, a few years ago, comments like "museum restaurants worth visiting even if you don't like art" began to appear. Nevertheless, the chefs of the best museum restaurants clearly understand that the location imposes certain obligations on them, and they consider it their main task

to "create a gastronomic framework for beautiful works of art"⁵. The things I want to mention now are the restaurants in the world's most famous museums³.

Museum of Modern and Contemporary Art (MOMA) - The museum collection includes about 150,000 works and many masterpieces of modern art. Before the pandemic, about 3 million people came to New York every year to see Picasso's *Les Femmes d'Alger*, Dalí's *Persistence of Memory*, Brancusi's *Bird in Space*, Waite's *Christina Universe*, Van Gogh's *Starry Night*, Warhol's *Soup Bowls*, and many others. It is of great importance for the history of art. This museum has a wonderful restaurant and is the first and very successful project of the most famous New York restaurateur Danny Meyer in the "museum" genre. In 15 years, the restaurant changed three chefs, but this did not affect the quality, and the collection of trophies is replenished every year. Received several awards from the James Beard Foundation (including "Best New Restaurant", "Best Wine Service", "Outstanding Design"), three stars (out of four) from *The New York Times* and three glasses from *Wine Spectator* been.. The menu ideologically corresponds to the concept of the museum, much of the so-called modern American cuisine is derived from an almost imperceptible but strong base of French classics. In addition to the main lounge and bar area, which serves cocktails and a la carte, the kitchen also has a four-person "chef's table"⁴.

Odette and the National Gallery of Singapore - The gallery opened in 2015 and is the largest museum in Singapore and Southeast Asia. His restaurant- In five years, Odette rose from a simple museum restaurant to a full collection of awards and number one on the list of Asia's 50 best restaurants. Julien Royer worked for the patriarch of French haute cuisine, Michel Bras, and brought his jewelry style to Singapore, but of course with his own interpretation. Royer combines the techniques and approach of nouvelle cuisine with products from around the world, carefully selected from Asian countries, Europe and Australia. The restaurant has an extensive and mostly classic wine list.

³ <http://uu.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1618807/FULLTEXT01.pdf>

⁴ Fredrik Gahmning Museum treats and shopping sprees: The role of shops and restaurants in a museum visit maqolasi.

Rex Whistler Restaurant and Tate Britain - One of the most famous museum restaurants will not be quarantined and may close forever. The reason is that full-length mural by Rex Whistler, which the artist painted specifically for its opening in 1927, and which the Tate was very proud of for many years. But in a hundred years, customs have changed, and now the board of trustees of the gallery is thinking about what can be done with the restaurant, where the multi-meter wall is occupied by the image of hunting in the forest, where black children are tied, and the images of caricatured Chinese have been revived. But it is technically impossible to remove it from the restaurant, so the management of the museum is seriously discussing its closure. If that doesn't happen, a restaurant with seasonal British food and one of London's most interesting wine lists could be back on us.

Le Franc and Fondation Louis Vuitton- Fondation Louis Vuitton is the latest addition to the list of Paris attractions. Bernard Arnault entrusted the design of the building for his modern art collection to the same Frank Gehry, who built a dazzling object in the Bois de Boulogne with dozens of luminous metal "sails" and a spectacular view of the Eiffel Tower. Inside is the Arno Collection itself, including works by Basquiat, Claude Monet, Yves Klein, Giacometti, Warhol and many others, as well as temporary exhibitions. The kitchen is led by seasoned chef Jean-Louis Nomico, who won a Michelin star for his Les Tablettes for modern haute French cuisine. The restaurant is named after Gehry, who designed it. During the day, the restaurant offers set-price lunches, in the evenings - a la carte dinners, several times a week they organize themed dinners dedicated to a particular product, wine or winery, or, for example, color or style.

Another great museum, located in New York, and in line with the museum's German and Austrian art exhibitions, the famous Café Sabarsky serves elegant pastries in an environment where you can easily imagine Adele Bloch-Bauer. Designed to look like a Viennese coffee house where intellectuals meet, the Sabarsky Café is decorated with lighting fixtures by Josef Hoffmann and furniture by Adolf Loos. In the corner of the cafe sits a Bösendorfer grand piano, used for the museum's popular cabaret series.

Thus, the contribution of restaurants in museums to the popularity of the museum is very high. It should be mentioned that not only the place to eat, but also the most frequent and frequent visits depend on the restaurants in the museum. At the same time, it ensures that some comforts are created for people. We see that the place and importance of restaurants in world museums is higher than we thought. Several dissertations have been written to prove this, including Fredrik Gahm's article "Museum treats and shopping sprees: The role of shops and restaurants in a museum visit. At the same time, several changes are taking place in our country regarding the development of museums and the dissemination of our history to the general public. For example, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is making several innovations regarding the development of tourism and museums, about the emergence of restaurants in museums. For this, they are creating all the conditions. In fact, museums are very important for the development of tourism in our country. Today, the museums of our country are being equipped, taking inspiration from world museums. At the same time, importance is being paid to the emergence of restaurants in museums. Of course, this will help increase the number of visitors.

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